

EVALUATION OF THE COMBINED EFFECT OF LEPANA AND PANA CHIKITSA IN YUVANPIDIKA

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ABSTRACT

Yuvanpidika is a common dermatological disorder of adolescence described in *Ayurveda* under *Kshudra Roga*. Acne is a chronic inflammatory condition of the pilosebaceous follicles on the face and upper trunk. *Aacharya Sushruta* has described *Yuvana Pidika* as the eruptions similar to *Shalmali* thorn on face especially of adolescents. It is also named as *Mukhadushika*. The condition is characterized by *Pidika* (papules/pustules) on the face, chest, and back due to vitiation of *Kapha*, *Vata*, and *Rakta doshas*. Changing lifestyle, irregular diet, and stress further aggravate the condition. The present study evaluates the effect of *Ayurvedic* management in the treatment of *Yuvanpidika* through a single case observation. In *Ayurvedic* texts, many *mukhlepa*, medicinal preparations, *Pathya Apathya*, and *Dinacharya* procedures have a wonderful preventive and curative effect on *Yuvanpidika* diseases. Furthermore, facial beauty is necessary for everyone, so all sections of *Ayurveda* can work together to prevent *Yuvanpidika* and other diseases.

KEYWORDS: *Yuvanpidika*, Acne Vulgaris, *Kapha-Vata-Rakta*, *Ayurvedic* management, *Raktaprasadana*.

INTRODUCTION

Yuvanpidika is a condition predominantly seen in young individuals, especially during puberty. The name itself is derived from *Yuvana* (youth) and *Pidika* (eruption). *Ayurveda* describes *Yuvanpidika* as *Mukha*, *Vaksha*, *Skandha sthita Pidika* — small, raised lesions that resemble *Shalmali Kantaka* (thorn of silk- cotton tree) and are caused due to vitiation of *Kapha*, *Vata* and *Rakta* (A.H. Nidana 14/45).

From a modern perspective, it corresponds to Acne Vulgaris, a multifactorial chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous unit. The main pathogenesis involves increased sebum production, follicular keratinization, bacterial colonization (*Cutibacterium acnes*), and inflammation.

In the *Ayurvedic* framework, improper diet (*Mithya Ahara*), excessive intake of oily and spicy food (*Snigdha*, *Ushna Ahara*), disturbed sleep, and stress lead to *Rakta*

dushti and *Kapha-Vata prakopa*, resulting in *Pidika utpatti*.

Ayurvedic management focuses on *Dosha-Shamana*, *Raktashodhana*, and *Twak Prasadana* using internal and external therapies.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To study *Yuvanpidika* (Acne Vulgaris) from *Ayurvedic* and modern perspectives.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of *Ayurvedic* management in a clinical case of *Yuvanpidika*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In *Ayurvedic* texts, many *mukhlepa*, medicinal preparations, *Pathya Apathya*, and *Dinacharya* procedures have a wonderful preventive and curative effect on *Yuvanpidika* diseases. Furthermore, facial beauty is necessary for everyone, so all sections of

Ayurveda can work together to prevent *Yuvanpidika* and other diseases.

AETIOPATHOGENESIS OF ACNE VULGARIS:

There must be three probable pathogenic factors responsible for causing the disease:

- 1) There is elevated level of sebum excretion. The sebum excretion level is directly proportional to the severity of acne but it is not the only causative factor for development of acne. The main accounting factor for the onset of acne in teenage is hormonal & even sebum excretion is also regulated by the hormones Androgens & Progesterones. Oestrogen reduces sebum excretion. However patients with absence of other clinical features have normal endocrine profile.
- 2) The Propionibacterium acnes is the relatively slow growing, typically aero tolerant anaerobic, gram positive bacterium (rod) linked to the skin condition of acne. It colonises the pilosebaceous ducts & acts on lipids to produce a number of pro inflammatory factors.
- 3) There is occlusion or blockage of pilo-sebaceous unit.

AETIOPATHOGENESIS OF YUVAN PIDIKA^[6]

In *Ayurvediya Samhita*, there is a brief description available regarding the disease *Mukhdushika*. In *Ayurvediya* Literatures it is describe under the heading of *Kshudra Rogas* & not as an independent disease. These diseases are called as *Kshudra* because of their lesser severity.

According to *Sushruta Samhita Nidana Sthana*, painful eruptions like thorn of *Shalmali*, impregnated with *meda* are found on the face of adolescent are called as *Mukhdushika* or *Yuvanpidika*. In Other *samhitas* of *Ayurveda* like *Ashtanga Hridaya* & *Ashtanga Samgraha* there is a description about *Mukhdushika* is almost similar.

According to the description of various *Samhitas*, the probable *Samprapti* of the disease as- due to the indulgence of the aetiological factors *Kapha*, *Vata* & *Rakta Dushti*, there will be vitiation of *Vata* & *Kapha Dosha* which gradually vitiates *Rasaraktaadi Dhatus*. It may causes abnormality in *Dhaatvaagni* (mainly *Medoagni*) resulting into excessive *Sweda* production (as *sweda mala* of *medodhatu*), which obstructs the hair follicle (as *meda* & *Lomakoopa* are the root of *Swedvaha Srotas*). Thus here *Sanga* type of *Srotodushti* takes place & its manifestation is *Mukhdushika*.

PURVARUPA: No *Purvarupa* of *Mukhdushika* is mentioned in *Ayurvediya Samhita*.

RUPA: The *Purvarupa* of the disease *Yuvanpidika* is not available in almost all the *Ayurvediya Samhitas* but the *Rupavstha* of the disease is explained by all the *Acharyas*. According to *Acharya Sushruta* – the *Pidika*

resembles like *Kantaka* of *Shalmali tree*. It is due to condition of *Kapha*, *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Rakta* are called as *Yuvanpidika*.

Shalmali Kantakakara Pitika- The eruption on face which looks like conical shape resembles with *Shalmali Kanta* is called as *Yuvan Pidika*.

Saruja- The eruptions are painful. The severity may vary from mild to severe.

Ghana- The word *Ghana* means solid, hard or indurated. The eruption is hard and thick.

Medogarbha – The eruption is filled with the *Meda*. It occurs due to obstruction of the *Medogranthi*.

Yuna Mukhe- This disease usually affects in adults. This word shows the site of origin of *Pidika* and time of occurrence of the disease.

CASE STUDY

Type of Study: Single case study (observational).

Selection of Patient: Patient diagnosed clinically with *Yuvanpidika*.

- Assessment Criteria: Reduction in number and size of *Pidika*,
- itching,
- burning sensation,
- pain, and
- post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation.

CASE REPORT

Patient Profile:

Name: Miss Akanksha Age: 19 years

Sex: Female

Occupation: College student

Chief Complaints

Eruptions on face since 1 year

Itching and burning sensation occasionally

Mild pain on pressing lesions

History of Present Illness: Gradual onset of eruptions on cheeks and forehead since one year, aggravated before menstruation and during periods of stress.

History of past illness - No any h/o of major illness.

History of allergies - No h/o any allergies.

Family H/O - No any significant family history

Personal History

Bowel - Constipated, 1 time / day, unsatisfactory evacuation Appetite -Reduced

Diet - Spicy and Sour food along with junk food once in week.

Micturation - Normal 3-4 times/day, 1-2times/night

Sleep - Disturbed sleep due to studies

Ashthavidh Pariksha

Nadi - 78/Min

Mala - *Asamayak* (constipated)

Mutra - *Samyak Jivha* - *Saam Shabda* – *Spashta*

Sparsh - Anushan Shita, Khar Sparsh Druk – Samyak Akriti – Madhyam

Post-acne marks: Present

Local Examination

Lesion type: Papules and pustules
Site: Cheeks, chin, and forehead
Color: Erythematous base
Pain: Mild on palpation

Ayurvedic Assessment

Dosha involvement: Kapha, Vata, Rakta
Dushya: Rakta, Meda
Srotas involved: Raktavaha, Medovaha
Rogamarga: Bahya marga
Vyadhi swabhava: Chirakari

Treatment Protocol

DRUGS	DOSE	ANUPANA	DURATION
1. <i>Gandhak Rasayana</i>	250mg twice a day	Luke warm water	2 months
2. <i>Arogyavardhini Vati</i>	250mg twice a day	Luke warm water	2 months
3. <i>Kaishora Guggulu</i>	250mg twice a day	Luke warm water	2 months

LEPA

MEDICATION	DOSAGE	TIME	DURATION
<i>Shalmali kantaka lepa</i>	5gm with milk	Once a day	2 months

Follow-up and Outcomes

Day	Observation
Day 15	Reduction in itching and burning sensation No new eruptions
Day 30	Reduction in number of papules and pustules
Day 45	Skin clearer with minimal new lesions
Day	Observation
	Residual hyperpigmentation showing gradual fading
Day 60	Complete relief from itching, burning, and pain, no new acne eruptions, skin appears healthy

CONCLUSION

In this case study, there was significant improvement was noted along with other GIT related problems and with this we can conclude that, *Nitya Virechan* and *lepa* along with internal medicine helps to disease condition of acne vulgaris.

RESULTS

The results observed after treatment – Improvement in signs and symptoms of the patient, 7-8 days after the treatment started. Significant relief was found in *Daha* (burning sensation), and *ghana* (thickness of *pidika*) and no new acne formed. Satisfactory improvement in *Saruja* (pain), *Daha* (burning sensation) etc.

DISCUSSION

Probable mode of action *Gandhak Rasayana*

Gandhak Rasayan is prepared by giving 12 *Bhavanas* of drugs to *Shuddha Gandhaka*. It is mainly indicated in the management of *Kushta Roga* it having antibacterial and antifungal properties along with acting on *Rakta Dhatu* and causes *Rakta Shodhan* (purification of blood). It also acts as *Rasayana* and helps in improving the digestion and skin complexion. Sulfur is used both internally and externally for treatment of diseases of skin. It reduces the *Kandu*, *Pidika*, *Raaga* and *Daha* by its *Rakta Shodhak*, *Vranaropak*, *Krumighna* and *Kushthaghna* properties.

Probable mode of action *Kaishora Guggulu*

Kaishora Guggulu contents *Tripahala*, *Guggulu*, *Guduchi*, *Sunthi*, *Trivrut*, *Danti* acts as *Shothahar* (anti inflammatory), *Vrana Shodhak*, *Rasayan* also acts as aging skin health promoter, natural blood cleanser.

Probable mode of action *Arogyavardhini Vati*

Arogyavardhini Vati contains *Kutaki*, *Triphala*, *Trikatu* and other drugs helps to balance *Tridosha*, indicated in skin disorders, analgesic, wound healing, and antipruritic properties, *Pachani* (digestive), *Dipani* (appetizer), *Pathya* (wholesome for channel), *Hridya* (cardio protective) *Malashuddhikari* (cleaning of waste materials from body) which helps in reducing symptoms of *Yuvanpidika*. Pungent drugs are beneficial for reducing burning sensation and itching.

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